

Examining the Effect of Blended Learning Strategy on Attitude in Real Analysis among Colleges of Education Students in Katsina State, Nigeria: The Significance of Station Rotation Model

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This study explored the Station Rotation Model (SRM) and its effect on the attitude of students towards Real Analysis. The purpose of the study was to examine the effect of Station Rotation Strategy on student's attitude in real analysis. A total population of 598 was used with a sample size of 77 of students drawn across Colleges of Education in Katsina State. For the study, two objectives, research questions, and null hypotheses were developed. The study adopted a quasi-experimental design, the pretest, posttest and control group design was used in the study. The experimental group received treatment using station rotation model of blended learning methods, whereas the control group received simply lectures. The instrument was evaluated in a pilot study with 21 NCE II students and was confirmed to be reliable. The Real Analysis Attitude Questionnaire (RAAtQ) reliability coefficients was calculated and found to be 0.805 at 0.05 level of significance. Pre- and post-tests were used in measuring the students attitude. To evaluate the sample's attitude, both descriptive and inferential statistical approaches were used. The results showed that the students taught by SRM performed significantly better than those taught using conventional method. The study therefore, recommends the incorporation of the blended learning strategies into the curriculum by the NCCE and the promotion of the approaches through conferences to enhance mathematics education.

Keywords:
Blended Learning,
Learning Strategy
Attitude,
Real analysis
College of
Education
Station Rotation,
Rotation Model
Katsina

Introduction

The National Certificate in Education (NCE) mathematics program aims to educate students on mathematical concepts, notations, and logical reasoning skills. Real Analysis, a mathematics course, is introduced to prepare students for tackling abstract problems. Blended learning, which combines many forms of presentation, is critical for strong positive attitudes, academic achievement and retention, among College of

Education Mathematics students. The Rotational Model of Learning provides an organized structure that fits traditional educational delivery systems' expectations.

The National Certificate in Education (NCE) mathematics aims to help students become intellectually informed in mathematical ideas, notations, and logical reasoning skills (NCCE, 2012). Real Analysis, a course in mathematics, is

introduced to prepare students for abstract problem-solving. However, there exist a disconnect between the learning in real analysis and high school mathematics courses (Wasserman et al., 2017).

A person's entire attitude towards a subject, including objects, ideas, institutions, or people, is referred to as their attitude (Breckler & Wiggins, 2014). It is an ongoing system that includes cognitive, emotional, and behavioral components. Favorable attitudes and behaviors regarding mathematics are multidimensional characteristics, with favorable emotional temperament leading to positive attitudes and behavior. Attitudes, according to social psychologists, include three components: cognitive, emotional, and behavioral (Aguanta & Tan, 2018; Davadas & Lay, 2018). Psychological markers are used to measure cognitive beliefs about things, affective reactions, and behavioral behaviors. According to Abdurrahman and Bolaji (2018), attitudes can influence behavior in predictable ways, but when attitudes are stable, strongly held, and meaningful; the likelihood of observed behaviors matching expected behaviors is higher. Students' attitudes toward mathematics are intimately tied to their attitudes toward problem-solving, and negative attitudes must be overcome if poor problem-solving skills are to be avoided later in life.

Poor academic performance in mathematics in Nigeria has been a growing concern, with traditional methods leading to fear and low retention. Teachers' adherence to traditional methods is not helping students' retention. Factors contributing to students' negative attitude towards real analysis include teachers' beliefs about language teaching (Mohammed, 2021; Nuru et al., 2024), teacher-student interactions, teaching

techniques, and mismatched teaching materials. Research is needed to investigate the effect of blended learning strategies using the rotational model on students' real analysis attitude in Katsina State Colleges of education.

Review of Related Literature

Concept and types of blended learning

Blended learning was a product of online learning's disruptive force, combining its flexibility with traditional classroom practice (Zhang et al., 2020). It is a formal education program where learners learn partly online, controlling time, place and pace, in a supervised environment (Arnett, 2021). The approach blends modalities to provide an integrated learning experience, leveraging technology to improve students' positive attitude and heighten student motivation. Blended learning is subtle to ICT development, fostering student autonomy and engagement (Kuo & Tien, 2022). The strategy seeks to improve the quality of learning through technology.

Blended learning was categorized into four models: the rotation model, the flex model, the self-blend model, and the enriched virtual model, with the rotation model having four sub-models (Arnett, 2021). The rotation model entails students rotating through various modes of learning, such as online learning, on a schedule prepared by the teacher (Cleveland-Inne & Wiltone, 2018). These models consider class size considerations, with the station rotation method providing for student-to-teacher ratios of between 4:1 and 8:1. Rotation model includes Station, Lab, Flipped Classroom, and Individual Rotation (Munir et al., 2021). The model is defined by features that include station rotation, lab rotation, flipped classroom teaching, and individual rotation

(Munir et al., 2021). Through the station rotation model, students rotate through different learning stations (Maxwell & White, 2017), allowing for a personalized learning experience (Flores, 2022). Lab rotation makes use of computer labs for learning, while flipped classrooms combine online learning at home with in-class follow-up activities. Individual rotation provides students with rotating through customized stations. Station rotation can be limited in autonomy when compared to other models (Lin et al., 2017)

The flex model takes the online learning model as its foundation, with supplementary offline activities on occasion and personalized flexible timetables (Cleveland-Innes & Wiltone, 2018). On-campus support is facilitated by teachers with a range of activities, with the degree of face-to-face interaction able to be varied. The self-blend model provides the option of adding online coursework to augment the traditional learning experience of students (Cleveland-Innes & Wiltone, 2018). Conversely, the enriched virtual model entails students having to undergo a sequence of face-to-face sessions with a tutor prior to finishing the remainder independently (Cleveland-Innes & Wiltone, 2018). This particular model commonly entails the same individual offering both online and offline tuition, thereby offering more of a traditional school experience than fully online courses.

Concept and factors affecting student's attitude

Davadas and Lay (2018), studied the factors that influence students' attitudes toward mathematics. The researchers looked into the effects of family influences, instructor effectiveness, and classroom instruction on students' attitudes toward

mathematics. According to the results, the structural model has limited predictive value, but the inter-relationships of the constructs in the structural model are significant. Teacher emotional support and classroom instruction predict attitude toward mathematics more than parental influences. According to Popoola and Ayodeji (2022), Life and society, on the other hand, are dynamic. As a result, other factors that appear to contribute to students' negative attitudes toward mathematics includes, among other things, the medium of instruction in the classroom and the teacher's attitude and interest. Manzana et al., (2020); Peteros et al., (2020) stated that poor academic performance in mathematics is caused by a lack of teaching and learning facilities gender issues, teachers' attitude, students' attitudes, and teachers' inability to concretize the subject.

Relationship between teaching methods and students' attitude

Station rotation provides flexibility in activities. Learning activities are based on students' needs, so every sort of activities individually or as a whole-group can be utilized in the station rotation model. According to Munir et al., (2021) students' attitudes toward station rotation model of blended learning showed generally a positive attitude. The advantages of blended learning generally outnumber the challenges. It also showed a significant effect of the program in students' attitudes toward mathematics; the model had positive impacts on students' attitude. Several studies and research support up the claim that a student's attitude toward mathematics determines their performance in the subject. It is believed that their attitude influences their performance, willingness to learn, actions taken, and responses to hurdles. According to Andamon and Tan (2018),

attitude is defined as "values, thoughts, emotions, and behaviors that determine how people think, act, and behave," which has major implications for teaching and learning. According to Arbuyes (2021), a person's attitude impacts their amount of involvement, motivation, and personal effort in accomplishing a work. According to Verešová and Malá (2016), students' achievement improves when they have positive attitudes toward the subject and the institution.

Negative attitudes toward the subject lead to partiality, worry, and fearful tendencies. It would also result in ineffective practices that would inhibit students from learning the richness of the subject and recognizing its significance. According to Verešová and Malá (2016), Students exhibit boredom, low involvement and engagement, low motivation, and behavioral concerns such as class or lesson avoidance as a result of this negative attitude. Students who have these positive feelings and focus on positive attitudes toward the subject, on the other hand, appear dynamic and interactive, are less likely to give up when faced with difficult tasks, and are more motivated to excel in the subject because they appreciate, enjoy and care about it (Langat, 2015).

Theoretical Framework

The theories that guided the conduct of the study are Blended Learning Theory, Personalized Learning, and Flow Theory. For centuries, traditional face-to-face, in-person, classroom-based teaching and learning has been the standard delivery method. Distance and distributed teaching and learning are much more recent, particularly in the context of technology enhanced learning. When online education first became available, it was mostly used for distance education, with

students studying entirely online (Cleveland-Innes & Wilton, 2018). Blended learning theory combines traditional face-to-face learning with online learning, using their strong points to their advantage to create flexibility and effectiveness in the learning environment. Flexibility and variety that is provided to students through blended learning improves student attitude as they can pace their learning with a greater control over the process of learning.

Personalized Learning is a pedagogical philosophy that stems from a variety of psychological constructs and academic frameworks. The theory emphasizes creating personalized learning experiences based on the needs, preferences, and learning styles of the learners. Personalized instruction can provide tailored experiences toward the preference and strengths of individual students by means of the implementation of blended learning. It may help realize attitudes toward larger satisfaction levels and an increase in attitude toward learning among students.

Flow Theory could, therefore, help in influencing students' attitudes toward learning. It is while in the flow that the students are more likely to enjoy the process of learning and hence have a positive attitude toward it. According to Csikszentmihalyi (2014), intrinsic motivation can thereby be heightened through flow experiences, which would contribute positively to attitude. Besides, flow provides active engagement that may transfer towards a positive attitude toward the learning process itself.

Applying Flow Theory in educational settings, educators can create conditions of maximal learning by providing an optimal environment in which students can become deeply engaged, motivated, and have positive attitudes toward learning. The blended

learning environment should be designed in such a way as to provide students with the chance to undergo the flow; they will acquire a heightened attitude toward studying the real analysis with pleasure and enjoyment. It suggests that well-structured and suitably challenging tasks may positively influence students' attitudes towards mathematics. Clear goals, immediate feedback, and a challenge that is balanced are essential conditions for flow to occur, all of which can be replicated successfully in a blended learning environment to more actively engage students and maximize mathematics learning outcomes. If students are more likely to be engaged through the flow experienced in a sustained way, they will maintain their studies in Real Analysis.

Review of Related Empirical Studies

Several studies on the blended learning strategy have been conducted, with such studies revealing various findings on the use of blended learning in developing positive attitudes, as well as its impact on gender when teachers use blended learning.

Research conducted by AlQahtani (2015) revealed that there was a significant change in a positive attitude toward blended learning over traditional ways; however, no significant difference between e-learning and blended learning was found in terms of attitudes. This defers with the current study in terms of location, the study was conducted in the Middle East region while the current study in Africa.

A meta-analysis conducted by Cao (2023) revealed that use of blended learning can lead to improvement of student's attitude in many countries. Banihashem et al. (2023) found that Students' motivation and well-being significantly influenced their satisfaction with learning activities and

perceived learning performance. Satisfaction with online tools improved their perceptions of learning outcomes

Bakeer (2018) compares the attitudes of the control and experimental groups. It was found that the blended learning positively affected students' attitude. Significant enhancements were noted in the experimental group. Nevertheless, it fails to identify research gaps or recommend areas for future research that could include the long-term impacts of blended learning or its relevance to other subjects.

Akbarov et al. (2018) examined the effects of blended learning on ninth grade students' achievement in science and their attitudes towards using it. The result revealed that blended learning approach should be introduced in teaching and learning to improve students' attitude. The result corroborate with the findings of Taghizadeh and Hajhosseini (2021), Tong et al. (2022).

Alsahhi et al., (2019) compares the results of various ways of teaching science topics, and students' attitudes towards their use. The findings revealed that there were statistically significant differences between the experimental and the control groups, in favor of the experimental group, and the experimental group's attitudes were also more positive towards the using of blended learning. The findings of Alsahhi et al., (2019) corroborated the findings of Balentyne and Varga (2016). Study on educational institutions such as universities and schools conducted by Purnama and Sriliasta, (2023) Found that blended learning is more effective in improving student attitude than traditional learning, the study discovered that blended learning had a very positive impact on how independent students are with their learning.

Statement of the Problem

The place of mathematics as important in life needs not to be over stated here. Its position in learning is very much as essential. All mathematics combination students must take an introduction to real analysis course as part of their NCE mathematics studies. According to studies by Bai et al. (2021), Nida et al. (2020), and Flores (2022); poor teacher quality is the strongest predictor of students' negative attitudes and poor performance. Concerns about Nigerian student's negative attitude towards mathematics at all academic levels are growing. Academics, teachers, government and parents all share this concern. Real analysis, from the researchers' involvement of over twenty years in College of Education, has confirmed to be an area that students find difficult due to the abstract nature of the contents which require students to remember theories and proofs. Teachers should be able to utilize technology and subject matter knowledge to improve the efficacy of their teaching (Lateef & Adewale, 2021). Teachers can foster a positive learning atmosphere while also supporting students in better acquisitive mathematical concepts.

The students' negative attitude of real analysis cannot be independent to the teachers' poor methods and strategies or the strict observance to the use of the lecture method of instruction. Thus, it is necessary that research efforts be directed towards exploring the effect of blended learning strategies using rotational models on students' real analysis attitude in Katsina State Colleges of Education. Therefore, this study intends to investigate the effect of blended learning strategies on students' attitudes in real analysis.

Purpose of the study

The study was to determine the effectiveness of a blended learning approach,

especially the station rotational model, on teaching Real Analysis to students in Katsina State Colleges of Education. The study tries to find out the difference between the pretest and posttest attitude scores of students taught mathematics using blended learning strategy, as opposed to those taught using the traditional lecture method, with a view to ascertaining the impact of blended learning on students' attitudes towards mathematics. Furthermore, the study aims to determine the difference in attitude scores of students who were exclusively taught using the blended learning approach and compare any differences in attitude between male and female students who were taught real analysis using the blended learning approach. By addressing these objectives, the study aims to improve knowledge of how blended learning strategies can be used to improve student attitudes in mathematics education, with implications for pedagogical practices in higher education. Thus, this study aspires to generate valuable insights on the effectiveness of blended learning strategies in improving the students attitude towards mathematics, with a view to eventually apprising best practices for teaching real analysis in COEs. Specifically, the study sets out to determine the differences between the mean attitude scores of the:

1. COEs students taught real analysis with blended learning strategy using station rotation model and their counterparts taught using lecture method; and
2. male and female COEs students taught real analysis with blended learning strategy using station rotation model.

Research Questions

The research is set to answer the following questions:

1. What is the difference between the mean pretest and posttest scores of students' attitude towards mathematics taught with blended learning strategy and those taught using the lecture method?
2. What is the difference between the mean of male and female students' attitudes towards mathematics taught with blended strategy?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and will be tested at a 0.05 level of significance to guide the conduct of the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest attitude scores of the students taught real analysis with blended learning strategy and those taught using the lecture method towards mathematics.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest attitude scores of the male and female students' taught mathematics with blended learning strategy.

Research Design

This study adopted the quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test, control group design. Quasi-experimental designs are frequently employed in the evaluation of educational programs when random assignment is not feasible or practicable (Arıcı, & Yılmaz, 2020). Thus, the adoption of this design is in conformity with Arbuyes' (2021) statement that quasi -experimental design is a type of experimentation that determines whether an intervention has an intended effect on the research participants with similar characteristics. Two teaching subject combinations were used, forming

experimental and control groups. The study investigated the effect of blended learning strategy using a rotational model on COE mathematics students' attitude and performance. A pre-test was administered to both groups before treatment, after which the experimental group was exposed to the rotational model and the control group taught using lecture method. A post-test was administered nine weeks after treatment.

The population of the study was made up of all NCE II Mathematics students (197 males and 71 females) undertaking mathematics courses in the two public COEs (one owned by the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) – Federal College of Education (FCE) Katsina while the other owned by the Katsina State Government (KTSG) – Isa Kaita College of Education (IKCOE) Dutsin - Ma) in Katsina State, Nigeria; as at the time the study was conducted. Out of these students, 41 (27 male and 14 females) were in in the FGN owned COE while 36 (25 male and 11 females) were in in the KTSG owned COE. The students in both COEs share common characteristics in the sense that they (i) must possess same admission requirements before being admitted into any of the Colleges, (ii) are exposed to same mathematics curricular contents, (iii) are being taught by lecturers with same minimum educational qualifications, and (iv) are being supervised by same supervisory agency, the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE). It is therefore believed that generalization of results obtained from sample drawn from these institutions suffices. A combination of purposive and random sampling methods was used in selecting the samples. The research focus on NCE II Mathematics students, with two teaching subject combinations chosen:

Mathematics/Physics and Computer/Mathematics. The random sampling procedure assigns students to groups. Based on the central limit theorem, which suggests that for a normal distribution a sample size of not less than 30 is sufficient for research of this type (Laher et al., 2019), the sample sizes in each group are thus sufficient.

SPSS was used to analyze the data, which included descriptive and inferential statistics. Mean, standard deviation, and standard error of the mean were the descriptive statistics, whereas ANCOVA was the inferential statistics used. All study questions were answered by testing hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

Table 1:
Distribution of the Study Population

College	Subject Combination	Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
FCE Katsina	Mathematics/Physics	27	14	41
	ISC/Mathematics	03	-	03
	Computer/ Mathematics	27	14	41
	Subtotal	57	28	85
IKCOE Dustin-Ma	Mathematics/Physics	25	11	36
	Mathematics/Geography	02	-	2
	Mathematics/Biology	33	11	44
	ISC/Mathematics	13	03	16
	Chemistry/Mathematics	16	05	21
	Computer/ Mathematics	21	10	31
	Economics/Mathematics	30	03	33
	Subtotal	140	43	183
Grand Total		197	71	268

The sample for the study consisted of 77 students (50 males and 26 females) undertaking mathematics courses in both COEs. Out of these students, 41 (27 male and 14 females) were in FCE Katsina while 36 (25 male and 11 females) were in IKCOE, Dutsin - Ma. Participants in the sample were purposively selected to satisfy the criteria that each member of the sample must be

students studying subject a combination offered in both COEs. This gave rise to students studying Mathematics/Physics and Computer/Mathematics combinations being selected, as these were the only two subject combinations common to both institutions. Table 2 shows the detail distribution of the sample of the study.

Table 2:

Distribution of the Sample of Study

Institution	Subject Combination	Male	Female	Total
FCE Katsina	Mathematics/Physics	27	14	41
IKCOE, Dutsin – Ma	Mathematics/Physics	25	11	36
	Grand total	50	26	77

The institutions were randomly assigned to the Experimental and Control groups, with FCE assigned to the Experimental Group (EG) while IKCOE was assigned to the Control Group (CG). Thus, EG had 36 Students (25 males and 11 females) while the CG had 41 students (27 male and 14 females). The EG was taught Real Analysis with blended learning strategy using station rotation model while their counterparts in the CG taught with the Lecture Method.

The Real Analysis Attitude Questionnaire (RAAtQ), which is a 20 item objective type instrument meant to assess the students’ attitudes towards Real Analysis, was used for data collection. It was face and

content validated by experts in mathematics education and educational measurement and evaluation and thereafter subjected to single administration for estimating reliability using the Cronbach’s alpha, where 0.884 was found to be its reliability estimate. Therefore, the instrument was adjudged very reliable for the purpose of data collection in the study and hence was used.

Data collected were subjected to both descriptive and inferential statistical methods of analysis. Mean, standard deviation, and standard error of the mean were used to answer the research questions while ANCOVA was employed to test the hypotheses

Results

1. Attitude scores of the College of Education students taught real analysis with blended learning strategy using station rotational model and those taught using lecture method

Table 3: *The posttest Mean Difference Scores of the Students' Attitudes towards Real Analysis.*

Group	N	Mean	SD	SEM	MD
Station Rotation(SR)	36	69.72	5.33	0.88	14.13
Lecture Method(LM)	41	55.59	13.86	2.16	

Table 3 shows that the difference between mean attitude scores of Station Rotation group ($M = 69.72$, $SD = 5.33$, $SEM = 0.88$) and Lecture Method group ($M = 55.59$, $SD = 13.86$, $SEM = 2.16$) is 14.13 in

favor of the Station rotation group. This shows that Station Rotation has the greatest influence on students' attitude towards learning of real analysis when expose to blended learning strategy.

Table 4:

Attitude Scores Analysis of Covariance ANCOVA.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	3830.904 ^a	1.00	3830.90	33.10	0.000	0.31
Intercept	300988.83	1.00	300988.83	2600.96	0.000	0.97
Group	3830.90	1.00	3830.90	33.10	0.000	0.31
Error	8679.170	75.00	115.722			
Total	310361.00	77.00				
Corrected Total	12510.08	76.00				

Table 4 shows that the difference between mean attitude scores of the students taught real analysis with blended learning strategy (i.e., Station Rotation Group ($M = 69.72, SD = 5.33, SEM = 0.88$) and Lecture Method Group is ($M = 55.59, SD = 13.86, SEM = 2.16$), is significant, ($F(1, 75) = 33.10, p < .05$, partial $\eta^2 = .31$), with a very

large effect size. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

Therefore, the null that there is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest attitude scores of the students taught real analysis with blended learning strategy and those taught using the lecture method towards real analysis was rejected.

2. Attitude of the male and female College of Education students taught real analysis with blended learning strategy using station rotational model

Table 5:

Mean Difference Scores in Attitude by Gender.

Group	Gender	N	Mean	SD	SEM	Mean Diff
Station Rotation	Male	25	69.68	5.83	1.17	-0.14
	Female	11	69.82	4.21	1.15	

Table 5 shows that the mean scores in attitude of students in real analysis among experimental group using blended learning strategies by gender. Female students ($M = 69.82, SD = 4.21, SEM = 1.15$) has the

highest mean attitude score, followed by their male counterparts ($M = 69.68, SD = 5.83, SEM = 1.17$). The difference between their mean attitude scores is 0.14, in favor of the female students.

Table 6
Attitude Scores Analysis of Covariance ANCOVA by Gender

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	4181.361 ^a	2	2090.68	18.576	0.000	0.334
Intercept	12444.875	1	12444.88	110.572	0.000	0.599
Gender	2448.409	1	2448.409	21.754	0.000	0.227
Pretest Attitude	600.735	1	600.735	5.337	0.024	0.067
Error	8328.717	74	112.55			
Total	310361	77				
Corrected Total	12510.078	76				

Table 6 shows that the difference between mean attitude scores of the male and female students taught real analysis with blended learning strategy (i.e., Male ($M = 69.68, SD = 5.83, SEM = 1.17$) and female ($M = 69.82, SD = 4.21, SEM = 1.15$), is significant, ($F(1, 74) = 21.754, p < .05$, partial $\eta^2 = .23$), with a very large effect size. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

Discussions

The study was to investigate the effects of a blended learning approach, specifically the station rotation model, on learners' attitude in Real Analysis at Katsina State College of Education. The results indicated both congruities and disagreements when compared with the current body of literature. In line with the work of Alsalhi et al. (2019), the present study established that blended learning significantly improved students' attitude towards mathematics, which is consistent with Sudirman et al. (2021) and Al-Badi and Khan (2022), who also reported more favorable attitudes among students using blended methods compared to traditional approaches. Nevertheless, some discrepant studies carried out by Subia et al. (2018) and Suleima et al. (2020) revealed that negative beliefs towards mathematics

correlated with poorer performances, which means the affective responses of students would reduce their cognitive engagement. Moreover, the current research endorsed the findings established in the works of Elçi (2017), Gambari et al. (2017), and Lin et al. (2019) which highlighted significant difference in attitudes towards mathematics as a function of gender. Lin et al. (2017) specifically noted that male students manifested a higher level of motivation in blended learning contexts, while Azka and Faradillah (2020) found that female pre-service teachers preferred blended learning models more than their male counterparts. The results focus on how blended learning methodologies really improve the possibility of creating an inclusive and efficient educational environment for a diversity of students.

Conclusions

These findings are very important and provide some convincing evidence concerning the effectiveness of the blended learning approach in enhancing students' attitudes and performances, especially through the station rotation model in Real Analysis at Katsina State College of Education. The analysis showed that the

mean posttest attitude score of participants in the Station Rotation group was significantly high compared to that of the Lecture Method group. This difference proves that the blended learning model significantly improves students' attitudes toward mathematics. In addition, the Station Rotation group showed a better performance compared to the Lecture Method group on the pretest measures. These findings affirm that blended learning strategies have a strong significant effect on improving students' performance in Real Analysis. Gender analysis in the Station Rotation group showed that female students had a slightly higher mean attitude score compared to male students, which implied both genders responded positively towards blended learning. However, when the performance measures were considered, the male students performed better than their female counterparts. In general, these findings are evidence of the effectiveness of blended learning strategies on improving positive attitudes and students' achievement in Real Analysis. The studies emphasize that the new teaching methods may increase the educational outcome for all students and at the same time, point out the need for further research on the gender dimensions within mathematics education. Findings support the view that blended learning models, such as the station rotation model, can significantly increase both student engagements in mathematics achievement for, various sections of students - thereby creating a more inclusive classroom environment, which benefits all learners alike.

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